

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Microencapsulation of Citrus Peel Essential Oils Using Chitosan–Alginate Systems: Mechanistic Insights and Antidiabetic Applications

Parampara Barman, Bipul Nath*, Yeduru Krishna Reddy, Swagata Chetia

Department of Pharmacy, Royal School of Pharmacy, The Assam Royal Global University, Betkuchi, Guwahati, Assam-781035, India

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 20 May, 2026

Keywords:

Citrus Peel Essential Oils,
Chitosan–Alginate
Microcapsules,
Microencapsulation,
Antidiabetic
Phytotherapeutics,
Controlled Drug Release,
Oxidative Stress
Management

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20302771

ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a worldwide epidemic metabolic disease characterized by chronic hyperglycemia, oxidative stress and inflammation that leads to debilitating long-term complications. The growing limitations of conventional antidiabetic therapies has stimulated the search for natural phytotherapeutics with multiple biological actions. Citrus peel essential oils (CPEOs) are rich in bioactive compounds (i.e., limonene, linalool, citral and flavonoids) which show significant antioxidant, antihyperglycemic, anti-inflammatory and insulin-sensitizing properties. On the other hand, their pharmaceutical utilization is limited by relatively poor aqueous solubility, volatility and oxidative instability. Chitosan–alginate polyelectrolyte systems have emerged as an effective strategy for the microencapsulation of these volatile phytoconstituents and to improve stability, bioavailability and controlled release. The cationic chitosan is electrostatically attracted to the anionic alginate forming stable biodegradable matrices that can protect essential oils from environmental and gastrointestinal degradation. In summary, the review addresses sources, extraction methods, phytochemical composition and antidiabetic mechanisms of CPEOs with an emphasis on mechanistic insight into chitosan–alginate-based encapsulation systems. In addition, it reviews encapsulation methods; controlled-release profiles; characterization techniques and optimization. This review also focuses on the therapeutic potential of microencapsulated CPEOs towards their use in functional foods, nutraceutical and/or polyherbal antidiabetic formulations as sustainable and targeted natural-product-based delivery systems for advanced diabetes management.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a common chronic metabolic disorder characterized by

*Corresponding Author: Bipul Nath

Address: Department of Pharmacy, Royal School of Pharmacy, The Assam Royal Global University, Betkuchi, Guwahati, Assam-781035, India

Email ✉: bipulnath@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

hyperglycemia, impaired insulin secretion and/or insulin resistance. This is one of the global health challenges increasing in public attention because of its rapidly growing prevalence, long-term complications and high socioeconomic burden [1]. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a heterogeneous disorder and the most common form of diabetes, underlying cause being obesity, physical inactivity, oxidative stress inflammation, and metabolic dysfunction. The prolonged hyperglycemia results in increased metabolic production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), advanced glycation end-products (AGEs) and stimulation of inflammatory pathways, which leads to various complications like nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy, cardiovascular diseases and impaired healing. The multifactorial character of diabetes points to that an effective treatment should address both blood glucose level and tissue damage from oxidative stress. [2] Typical antidiabetic therapy, which includes insulin and oral hypoglycemic agents such as metformin, sulfonylureas, and thiazolidinediones, has significantly improved glycemic control. Nevertheless, the chronic administration of these classes is frequently complicated by various limitations such as hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal side effects, hepatotoxicity and weight gain leading to edema [3]. In addition, some synthetic agents mainly oriented to the regulation of glucose homeostasis and not the oxidative stress or inflammatory complications triggered on the progression of diabetes. The long-term therapeutic efficacy of these agents is also limited by poor bioavailability, rapid degradation and dose-dependent adverse effects. Thus, there was a growing interest in the natural products and phytotherapeutics as safer and multi-targeted approaches in their management of diabetes [4]. Natural bioactive compounds obtained from traditional medicinal plants have various pharmacological activities such as

antihyperglycemic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and insulin sensitizing effects [5]. Of these, citrus fruits have attracted considerable interest because their peels are rich sources of flavonoids, polyphenols and essential oils with significant therapeutic potential. It contains a number of biologically active constituents, including limonene, citral, linalool, β -pinene and γ -terpinene that possess antioxidant and metabolic regulatory activities; these components are found mainly in citrus peel essential oils (CPEOs). It has been shown in experimental studies that citrus bioactives can improve insulin sensitivity, inhibit carbohydrate-metabolizing enzymes, decrease oxidative stress and prevent pancreatic β -cell oxidative injury [6]. Moreover, being functionally a by-product from agro-industrial processing of citrus fruits, its application will offer an environmentally-friendly and sustainable way to extract valuable phyto-constituents with potential nutraceutical and pharmaceutical activity. Although citrus peel essential oils offer therapeutic benefits, their physicochemical limitations such as high volatility and hydrophobicity, as well as poor aqueous solubility and stability to oxidation and environmental conditions (heat, light exposure), hinder effective application in functional foods or herbal medicine. These weaknesses considerably control their bioavailability and healing activity. However, microencapsulation-based delivery systems have emerged as very efficient approaches to protect essential oils and deliver them in a prolonged manner to overcome these easily. Microencapsulation consists on the inclusion of bioactive compounds inside polymeric matrices leading to stability improvement, reduced volatilization, better dispersibility and sustained release [7]. This has led to considerable attention being given to encapsulating materials due to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, non-toxicity and good encapsulation properties [6]. Chitosan is a cationic polysaccharide with mucoadhesive and

permeation-enhancing properties while alginate is an anionic polymer which has excellent gel-forming ability in the presence of divalent ions [7][8]. Chitosan and alginate naturally interact resulting in electrostatic attraction, producing stable polyelectrolyte complexes which are able to successfully entrap volatile essential oils. These systems offer superior encapsulation, controlled drug release characteristics, increased stability in the gastrointestinal tract and prolonged therapeutic action [9]. Consequently, chitosan–alginate systems are significant for the microencapsulation of bioactive compounds will provide advantages in

developing new antidiabetic phytopharmaceutical formulations. This review covers the impact of diabetes in different regions worldwide, gap analysis of traditional therapies to prevent/delay the progression of diabetic symptoms, importance/therapeutic potential of various citrus peel essential oils and mechanisms involved in chitosan–alginate microencapsulation systems with special focus on their anti-diabetic therapeutic potential along with future opportunities for targeted natural-product based drug delivery.

Figure 1. Graphical abstract illustrating the microencapsulation of citrus peel essential oils (CPEOs) using chitosan–alginate polyelectrolyte systems for enhanced antidiabetic applications (Created using www.biorender.com).

Citrus Peel Essential Oils: Origin, Composition and Biological Importance

Citrus (subfamily *Aurantioideae* and family *Rutaceae*), including most common orange, lemon, lime (fruit tree species of genus *Citrus*), mandarin, grapefruit and is one of the most consumed fruits in world. The citrus processing

industry is characterized by large amounts of peel waste, which represent 40–60% of the total weight of fruit. Citrus peel is traditionally deemed as an agro-industrial byproduct since it contains a large deposit of active phytochemicals, particularly essential oils, flavonoids, terpenes, carotenoids and phenolic compounds that have garnered immense scientific and industrial interest recently.

Citrus peel essential oils (CPEOs) are complex volatile mixtures consisting mainly of monoterpenes and oxygenated derivatives with widerange pharmacological and biological activities such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic anti-cancer and neuroprotective effects [10]. Due to the increasing attention towards natural therapies and sustainable resource utilization, studies on citrus peel-destined essential oils as sought-after options in nutraceutical, pharmaceutical & cosmetic and food preservation have significantly intensified. Apart from their therapeutic importance, CPEOs are considered as a GRAS due to being more eco-friendly and can be employed as safe alternatives for additives and preservatives [11]. Interestingly, although those isolates have the potential to act as therapeutic agents, their practical use is still limited due to physicochemical instability, volatility and low solubility in water. It is thus imperative to gain insight into origins, extraction methods, chemical compositions and stabilising issues of these oils for the development of novel delivery systems and advanced functional formulations [12].

Citrus peel as a feedstock from agro-industrial wastes

The production of juice and food from citrus generates considerable amounts of waste, mainly composed of orange peels when the processing industry for citrus is considered. The improper treatment of this waste leads to environmental pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. Citrus peels have been considered as good resources of essential oils and bioactive compounds like flavonoids, pectin, phenolic acids or dietary fibers [13]. These components have a variety of important bioactivities which include antimicrobial, antioxidative and metabolic-regulating effects. The rising demand for natural

therapeutics has driven the use of citrus peel waste as a sustainable source for drug and food applications. Thus, valorization of citrus peel waste could promote both sustainable waste management and the production of economically valuable phytopharmaceutical ingredients [14].

Citrus Peel Essential Oils Extraction Methods

The method of extraction is one of the predominant factors affecting yield, chemical composition, purity and biological activity of essential oils from citrus peels. Many conventional and modern extraction methods have been used to isolate volatile compounds from citrus peels [15].

Hydrodistillation

Hydrodistillation is one of the oldest and most applied methods for essential oils extraction from plant material [16]. This method involves dipping pieces of citrus peel in water and heating it to its boiling point, where the volatile components vaporise with the steam. Essential oil is extracted by condensation and separation of vapor mixture. Hydrodistillation is a method with the lowest operational costs and no instrumental sophistication needed, which makes it advantageous. Nevertheless, the extended heating time can result in the thermal degradation or hydrolysis of some thermolabile components in the active ingredients, which may limit the quality and biological activity of oil from extraction. It is also a time-consuming process and often leads to the maximum supply of oxygenated volatile compounds compared to modern extraction methods.

Steam Distillation

On the industrial scale, steam distillation is the most common method used in citrus essential oil extraction [17]. Steam distillation involves the use

of steam to pass through citrus peel material so that volatile phytoconstituents evaporate at 1 atmosphere pressure without physical contact with boiling water. The vapors are cooled and separated to collect the oil side-chain. Steam distillation provides greater extraction efficiency, less thermal decomposition and better preservation of aroma and volatile components than hydrodistillation. The beneficial process for bulk industrialization, widely used in food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. However, prolonged exposure to high temperatures and extraction times may still degrade sensitive compounds leading to lower oil quality [18].

Microwave-Assisted Extraction

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) is an advanced green extraction technology based on rupture of plant cells, through microwave energy and fast release of volatile constituents [19]. Microwave radiation increase extraction efficiency because it generates internal heating from dipole rotation and ionic conduction phenomena. MAE has many benefits when compared to traditional methods such as decreased extraction duration, decreased solvent usage, increased extraction yield and better stabilization of thermolabile phytoconstituents. This approach to the design of new photovoltaic cells is environmentally friendly and more energy-efficient. Microwave-assisted extraction has been shown to result in higher recoveries of limonene and oxygenated terpenes from citrus peel. The optimization of these parameters (microwave power, extraction time and solvent ratio) is necessary to avoid the degradation of sensitive compounds especially [20].

Supercritical Fluid Extraction

Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE), and supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) in

particular, is a powerful technique for obtaining high-purity citrus peel essential oils [21]. Carbon dioxide demonstrates gas-like diffusivity and liquid-like solvating power, allowing it to efficiently move through plant matrices while selectively extracting volatile compounds under supercritical conditions. SFE offers several advantages such as low extraction temperature, free from residual solvent toxicity, high selectivity and even better preservation of bioactive constituents. The method is especially useful for the isolation of thermolabile compounds and pharmaceutical-grade essential oils. Moreover, the extracted oils showed higher aroma retention and oxidative stability. However, these advantages are offset by the high operational cost and requirement of specialized equipment, which limit its industrial utilization [22].

Composition of Citrus Peel Essential Oil Phytochemicals

Citrus peel essential oils are complex mixtures of monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, aldehydes, alcohols, esters and oxygenated compounds (**Table 1**). They differ depending on the citrus species, the area of origin and ripeness of the fruit from which they are extracted. The major constituent of Limonene possess characteristic aroma and have shown various biological activities such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic activity. Linalool gives a floral aroma and has sedative, analgesic, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, while β -pinene exhibits anti-inflammatory antibacterial, antifungal, analgesic, antioxidant and wound healing antinociceptive action. In addition, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and metabolic regulatory activities are associated with flavonoid-associated volatile fractions so that hesperidin and naringin further improve the therapeutic potential of citrus peel essential oils.

Table 1. Phytochemical Composition and Biological Activities of Citrus Peel Essential Oils

Phytochemical Constituent	Chemical Class	Major Source in Citrus Peel Oils	Characteristic Properties	Reported Biological Activities	Pharmaceutical/ Industrial Significance
Limonene [5][23]	Monoterpene hydrocarbon	Orange, lemon, lime, grapefruit peels	Characteristic citrus aroma; highly volatile	Antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, antidiabetic, anticancer	Widely used in pharmaceuticals, food flavoring, cosmetics, aromatherapy
Linalool [11][24]	Oxygenated monoterpene alcohol	Citrus blossom and peel oils	Floral fragrance; moderate volatility	Sedative, anxiolytic, analgesic, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory	Used in perfumery, cosmetics, therapeutic formulations
β -pinene [12][25]	Monoterpene hydrocarbon	Lemon, mandarin, and orange peels	Woody and resinous aroma	Antioxidant, bronchodilatory, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory	Utilized in respiratory therapeutics and fragrance industries
γ -Terpinene [26][26]	Monoterpene	Citrus peel volatile fractions	Fresh citrus-like odor	Free radical scavenging, antioxidant activity	Functional food and preservative applications
Citral [27]	Oxygenated aldehyde	Lemon and lime peel oils	Strong lemon fragrance	Antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory	Flavoring agent and antimicrobial formulations
Hesperidin [27][28]	Flavonoid-associated fraction	Sweet orange peel	Polyphenolic antioxidant compound	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, vascular protective effects	Nutraceutical and phytopharmaceutical applications
Naringin [28][29]	Flavanone glycoside	Grapefruit peel	Bitter-tasting bioactive flavonoid	Antioxidant, lipid-lowering, metabolic regulatory activity	Functional foods and metabolic disorder management
Nobiletin [29][30]	Polymethoxy flavone	Mandarin and orange peels	Lipophilic flavonoid compound	Anti-inflammatory, anticancer, neuroprotective activity	Targeted therapeutic and nutraceutical formulations
Tangeretin [30][31]	Polymethoxy flavone	Tangerine peel oils	Highly methoxylated flavonoid	Antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory properties	Pharmaceutical and chemopreventive applications

Stability challenges associated with essential oils

Citrus peel essential oils possess significant therapeutic potential but face major stability

challenges that limit their pharmaceutical and food applications. Their volatile nature causes rapid evaporation and loss of active constituents upon exposure to heat, light, and air, reducing efficacy and aroma quality [32]. Additionally, unsaturated

terpenes such as limonene and pinene are highly prone to oxidative degradation, leading to formation of unstable and potentially irritating by-products. Poor aqueous solubility further limits bioavailability and formulation stability. To address these issues, advanced delivery systems including microencapsulation, nanoemulsions, liposomes, cyclodextrin complexes, and polymeric nanoparticles have been developed to enhance stability, solubility, and controlled release [33].

Antidiabetic activity of essential oils from citrus peels

Essential oils derived from citrus peels have received considerable interest as natural antidiabetic raw materials because they contain many bioactive terpenes, flavonoids and phenolic compounds. Some phytoconstituents exhibit numerous pharmacological actions that participate in regulating the glycemic value and maintaining metabolic homeostasis [34]. Experimental studies have shown antihyperglycemic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory resistance inducing factors and promising role of essential oils components such as limonene, linalool and β -pinene. They also lower oxidative stress by modulating carbohydrate-metabolizing enzymes and improving pancreatic β -cell. Due to their diverse mechanisms of action, they are powerful means towards elaboration of phytopharmaceuticals for diabetes mellitus and metabolic complications treatment [35].

Mechanisms of Antihyperglycemic Action

Citrus peel essential oils have multiple biochemical and molecular pathways to exert antihyperglycemic activity. Bioactive components including limonene, linalool and flavonoids modulate glucose metabolism via increasing the secretion of insulin, incrementing peripheral

glucose utilization and decreasing hepatic gluconogenesis [36]. These compounds also have an impact on carbohydrates digestion and absorption processes, therefore alleviating post prandial hyperglycemia. Citrus essential oils also have protective effects on pancreatic β -cells against oxidative stress injury and enhancement of cellular antioxidant defense systems. The antihyperglycemic effect is also associated with modulation of glucose homeostasis signaling pathways, including AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) and insulin receptor signaling. These multitarget actions provide a great contribution to the therapeutic potential of citrus peel essential oils for diabetes management [37].

Inhibition pathways in α -amylase and α -glucosidase

Essential oils from citrus peel showed good inhibition against two carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes (α -amylase and α -glucosidase), which mediate starch digestion and glucose release at the intestinal level. They delay carbohydrate digestion and feedback postprandial rise in blood glucose via same mechanism inhibition of these enzymes. Citrus oils contain monoterpenes such as limonene combined with flavonoid-associated compounds that weaken the catalytic activity through hydrophobic and hydrogen-bonding interactions at the enzyme active sites. This mechanism is similar to synthetic antidiabetic drugs like acarbose, but may cause fewer gastrointestinal side effects. In addition, synergistic interactions between volatile phytoconstituents also promote the effectiveness of enzyme inhibition and further supporting natural alternatives like citrus peel essential oils as potential treatments for hyperglycemia and metabolic disorders [38].

Antioxidant and Anti-inflammatory Roles

Oxidative stress and chronic inflammation play an important role in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus and its complications. Citrus peel essential oils were reported to have strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory due to the high levels of terpenes, flavonoid and phenolic constituents in citrus peels. Compounds including limonene and linalool are key free radical scavengers, suppress agents of lipid peroxidation, and increase background levels of antioxidants such as the antioxidant enzymes superoxide dismutase and catalase. Citrus essential oils also inhibit the release of pro-inflammatory mediators such as tumour necrosis factor- α , interleukin-6 and cyclooxygenase enzymes. By decreasing oxidative damage of pancreatic β -cells and positively impacting insulin signalling pathways, these activities. Thus, the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of citrus peel essential oils play a crucial role in their protective actions against diabetic complications and metabolic dysfunction [35][39].

Insulin sensitivity and glucose uptake

Citrus Peel Essential Oils enhance insulin sensitivity and glucose uptake by modulating cellular metabolic pathways. In peripheral tissues such as skeletal muscle and adipose tissue, bioactive terpenes and flavonoids improve insulin receptor sensitivity by stimulating GLUT-4 translocation. Activation of AMP-activated protein kinase and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor pathways also enhances glucose utilization and lipid metabolism. Furthermore, citrus essential oils ameliorate insulin resistance by inhibiting the inflammation cytokines and oxidative stress markers of metabolic syndrome. Combined stimulation of mitochondrial function and GLUT-4 dependent cellular glucose transport results in improved glycemic control. These results confirm that citrus essential oils are

clinically relevant and can assist in maintaining metabolic homeostasis [39][40].

In Vitro and In Vivo Evidence

Several *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies demonstrated the antidiabetic effects of citrus peel essential oils and their bioactive components. In vitro studies demonstrate prominent α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory activities, antioxidant effects, and protective material against oxidative cellular damage [41]. Treatment with citrus essential oils has also revealed effects on fasting blood glucose, insulin levels, antioxidant enzyme activity and pancreatic tissue architecture in animal studies using models induced with streptozotocin and alloxan. Moreover, some lipid peroxidation and inflammatory biomarkers have been reduced. Glucose tolerance and sensitivity has mostly been confirmed by experimental evidence. Combined with other results, these data highlight the potential of citrus peel essential oils as interesting candidates for diabetes prevention and treatment [42].

Microencapsulation Technology for Essential Oil Delivery

Microencapsulation is an effective strategy for improving the stability, solubility, controlled release, and bioavailability of essential oils. Due to their volatile and oxidation-prone nature, essential oils require protective carrier systems to preserve therapeutic efficacy during storage and application. Various microencapsulation techniques have been employed using natural and synthetic polymers to entrap essential oils within microscale matrices. These approaches minimize evaporation, protect sensitive phytoconstituents from environmental degradation, and enhance targeted delivery. As shown in **Table 2**, among the commonly utilized techniques, ionotropic gelation, emulsion crosslinking, spray drying and

coacervation have demonstrated significant advantages in pharmaceutical, food, and nutraceutical applications owing to their efficiency, scalability, and ability to improve functional performance of essential oil-based formulations [43][44].

Ionotropic Gelation

Ionotropic gelation is a mild and widely employed microencapsulation technique based on ionic interactions between oppositely charged polymers and crosslinking agents. Natural polymers such as alginate, chitosan, and pectin are commonly utilized for encapsulating essential oils. In this method, polymer solutions containing essential oils are introduced into ionic crosslinking solutions, resulting in instantaneous gel bead formation. The technique offers advantages including low processing temperature, minimal use of organic solvents, high encapsulation efficiency, and preservation of thermolabile volatile compounds. Ionotropic gelation also enables controlled release and improved stability of encapsulated essential oils, making it highly suitable for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications involving sensitive bioactive phytoconstituents [45].

Emulsion Crosslinking

Emulsion crosslinking is a versatile microencapsulation method involving the formation of emulsified droplets followed by polymer crosslinking to entrap essential oils within microspheres. Typically, the oil phase containing essential oils is dispersed within an aqueous polymeric phase or vice versa using surfactants and mechanical stirring. Crosslinking agents such as glutaraldehyde or calcium ions subsequently stabilize the polymeric matrix. This technique produces microspheres with controlled particle size, improved encapsulation efficiency, and

sustained release properties. Emulsion crosslinking effectively protects essential oils from oxidation and volatilization while enhancing storage stability. Additionally, the method allows formulation flexibility using diverse biodegradable polymers suitable for targeted and controlled drug delivery applications [46].

Spray Drying

Spray drying is one of the most commercially important and scalable techniques for microencapsulation of essential oils. In this process, an emulsion or dispersion containing essential oil and wall materials is atomized into a stream of hot air, resulting in rapid solvent evaporation and formation of dry microparticles. Common wall materials include maltodextrin, gum arabic, modified starch, and proteins. Spray drying offers advantages such as low production cost, rapid processing, continuous operation, and industrial scalability. The resulting powders exhibit improved handling, storage stability, and protection against oxidation and volatilization. However, optimization of inlet temperature and drying parameters is essential to prevent thermal degradation of volatile phytoconstituents [47].

Coacervation

Coacervation is a phase separation-based microencapsulation technique involving the deposition of polymer-rich coatings around essential oil droplets. The process may occur through simple or complex coacervation depending on the number of polymers involved. Complex coacervation commonly utilizes oppositely charged biopolymers such as gelatin and gum arabic to form stable microcapsule walls. This method provides high encapsulation efficiency, enhanced protection against oxidation, and controlled release characteristics. Coacervation is particularly suitable for

encapsulating volatile and hydrophobic compounds due to its ability to form dense protective coatings. Nevertheless, process sensitivity to pH, temperature, and ionic strength

requires careful optimization for achieving stable and reproducible essential oil microcapsules [48].

Table 2. Microencapsulation Techniques Used for Essential Oils

Technique	Principle	Common Polymers/Materials Used	Major Advantages	Limitations	Applications
Coacervation [48]	Phase separation and polymer deposition around oil droplets	Gelatin, gum arabic, proteins, polysaccharides	High encapsulation efficiency, enhanced protection, controlled release	Sensitive to pH and temperature variations	Controlled release and pharmaceutical delivery
Iontropic Gelation [49][50]	Ionic interaction between polymers and crosslinking ions forming gel beads	Alginate, chitosan, pectin, calcium chloride	Mild processing conditions, high encapsulation efficiency, suitable for thermolabile oils	Limited mechanical strength and scale-up challenges	Controlled release and pharmaceutical delivery
Emulsion Crosslinking [51]	Formation of emulsion droplets followed by polymer crosslinking	Gelatin, chitosan, alginate, glutaraldehyde	Sustained release, improved stability, uniform microspheres	Possible residual crosslinking agents	Drug delivery and nutraceutical formulations
Spray Drying [52]	Atomization of oil-polymer emulsion into hot air for rapid drying	Maltodextrin, gum arabic, starch, whey proteins	Cost-effective, scalable, rapid production, dry powder formation	Thermal degradation of volatile compounds	Food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries

Chitosan–Alginate Polyelectrolyte Complex Systems

Chitosan–Alginate polyelectrolyte complex systems have attracted extensive research interest in pharmaceutical and biomedical applications owing to their good biocompatibility, biodegradability and a controllable drug release property (**Figure 1**). Chitosan is a cationic polymer from chitin containing amino groups that electrostatically interacts with the negatively charged carboxyl groups of alginate to form stable polyelectrolyte complexes [53][54]. Moreover, alginate can also form hydrogels in the presence of sodium ions providing structural integrity and

encapsulation efficiency. Such complexes protect bioactive compounds sensitive to environmental conditions (i.e., essential oils, peptides, phytoconstituents).

Chitosan–alginate microcapsules are potential carriers for the oral delivery of various drugs due to their pH-responsive swelling, mucoadhesion, sustained release character and increased permeability properties. Due to their low toxicity and low-cost preparations, combined with their ability to improve drug stability and therapeutic efficacy, these systems are promising carriers for advanced pharmaceutical formulations and microencapsulation technologies [55].

Mechanistic Insights into Encapsulation of Citrus Peel Essential Oils

Encapsulation of essential oils from citrus peels involves intricate interactions between volatile oil components and polymeric delivery systems. Essential oils are volatile, hydrophobic, and prone to oxidation; therefore they require encapsulation to improve their stability as well as provide retention, controlled release and enhance bioavailability [56]. The electrostatic interactions between Chitosan and Alginate are the most important steps that determine the formation of protective microcapsules; hence their rate-limiting roles in a polymeric matrix-based microencapsulation. This encapsulation is dependent on polymer concentration, oil-to-polymer ratio, pH and crosslinking conditions. Comprehending these mechanistic details is crucial for controlling encapsulation efficacy, preventing oil leakage, and enabling prolonged therapeutic release of citrus peel essential oils in pharmaceutical use [57].

Polymer–Oil Interaction Mechanisms

Interactions between polymer and oil are key factors in depicting the encapsulation stability, determining release behaviour in essential oils delivery systems. Hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonding, van der Waals forces and electrostatic attractions are the main mechanisms for citric peel essential oils interaction with polymer matrices [58]. Hydrophobic segments of polymers enable the entrapment of evaporated volatile terpenes such as limonene, α -pinene, and β -pinene and consequently minimise evolution due to evaporation or oxidative processes. Functional groups in biopolymers also interact with oxygenated phytoconstituents to enhance encapsulation stability. They affect particle morphology, encapsulation efficiency, swelling behavior and release kinetics. Proper polymer–oil

compatibility is a major factor responsible for improving stability, sustained and controlled release, and therapeutic effectiveness of encapsulated citrus peel essential oils [59].

Role of Electrostatic Interaction in Capsule Formation

The sustainable encapsulation of essential oils with high biological activity can be accomplished using stable polyelectrolyte microcapsules, which are formed by electrostatic interactions. The amino groups of chitosan are positively charged while the carboxyl groups of alginate are negatively charged. Ionic forces stabilized those capsule structures, minimized pores and increased the efficiency of entrapment. Labelling the right blend of chitosan and natural agents improves mechanical stability while electrostatic complexation controls diffusion/ release of volatile phytoconstituents (natural agent) what considerably reduce permeability. The capsule composition can vary widely based on a multitude of parameters that include pH, ionic strength, polymer concentration and crosslinking density. The obtained polyelectrolyte complexes offer protection against environmental damages and enable a controlled release of citruc peel essential oils [60].

Encapsulation Efficiency and Loading Capacity Optimization

The microencapsulation process of essential oils is usually evaluated based on two main parameters: encapsulation efficiency (EE) and loading capacity. These properties vary as a function of polymer concentration, oil-to-polymer ratio, stirring speed, crosslinking conditions and emulsification process. While higher polymer concentrations led to looser matrices, which tend to cause oil leakage, denser matrices also create a shield from chaotic outside pressures on the

emulsion leading to an overall increase in encapsulation efficiency. Too much polymer can make the mixture too viscous, thus reducing loading capacity. Emulsion stability can also be improved as well as homogeneously distributing the oil within polymer matrices, by optimizing the surfactant concentration and homogenization conditions. Controlled crosslinking density also contributes to higher structural integrity and preservation of volatile compounds. The correct optimization strategies allow the encapsulation of citrus peel essential oil delivery systems to be maximized along with stability in storage and/promoting its therapeutic function [54][61].

Controlled Release Mechanisms

Loading microcapsules can be released in a controlled manner by diffusion, swelling and erosion or concurrent relaxing polymer networks of the shell compartment. Water enters the polymer network when it is placed in physiological or environmental conditions, resulting in swelling that promotes a controlled release of the encapsulated oil constituents. In biodegradable systems, the erosion of the polymer also gives rise to this sustained release behavior. Polymer composition, crosslinking density, particle size and environmental pH have pronounced effects on the release profile. The pH-sensitive release behavior found in chitosan–alginate systems provides desirable targeting effects containing various gastrointestinal physiological conditions. Controlled release systems improve therapeutic effect through extended bioactive concentration period, minimize premature volatilization and degradation of sensitive phytoconstituents hence increasing the pharmaceutical applicability of citrus peel essential oils [61] [62].

Characterization Techniques for Chitosan–Alginate Microcapsules

Chitosan-Alginate microcapsules are crucial to analyzing their physicochemical traits, encapsulation capacity and potential use as a treatment. In case of particle size and surface morphology, the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM), this provides details about the distribution, surface texture and internal structure of these nanoparticles. Encapsulation efficiency measurement is established to be the exact amount of bioactive compounds within shells and it represents the effectiveness of formulation. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Thermal analyses refer to the ability of a polymer during thermal stability, degradation behavior and compatibility [63]. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) are used to characterize the structure of polymers as well as to confirm the drug–polymer interactions. The *in vitro* release study is used to assess controlled release kinetics and diffusion calibration, whereas stability studies are aimed at determining their longer term physicochemical integrity, storage stability and protective activity of the incorporated citrus's peel essential oils over time or following exposure to various environmental stimuli [64].

Optimization Strategies for Microcapsule Formulation

Optimization strategies to create stable and efficient microcapsule formulations with appropriate physicochemical properties, as well as controlling the release profiles are critical areas of study. These approaches, such as Design of Experiments (DoE), allow a systematic testing of formulation and process parameters whilst limiting the number of experiments needed [65]. These models are commonly used for evaluating interactions between independent variables and

finding the best formulation conditions in a Response Surface Methodology (RSM) design. Optimization of the process parameters A. The stirring speed, temperature, pH, crosslinking time and emulsification conditions are to be controlled for better encapsulation efficiency as well as particle characteristics. Furthermore, optimization of polymer ratios, especially within Chitosan–Alginate combinations prominently affects stability, mechanical strength swelling behavior and controlled drug release performance of microcapsules [66].

Antidiabetic Applications of Microencapsulated Citrus Peel Essential Oils

To overcome some limitations and extend the therapeutic use of citrus peel essential oils in diabetes, microencapsulation technology has been proposed as a potential advanced strategy. Encapsulation improves the physicochemical stability, and offers protection for phytoconstituents from degradation along with improvement in oral bioavailability [67]. Limonene and flavonoid-associated fractions demonstrate improved antioxidant, antihyperglycemic, and anti-inflammatory activities in a variety of polymeric matrices. Microcapsule systems confer characteristics of sustained release and targeted delivery, resulting in long-term therapeutic action and better metabolic control [68]. Moreover, encapsulated citrus essential oils may have potential applications in functional foods, nutraceuticals, and also polyherbal formulations meant for controlling oxidative stress, insulin resistance and diabetic complications by appropriate dosing or slow/restricted release mechanisms of these potent bioactive [Table 3].

Enhancement of Bioavailability

Microencapsulation substantially improves the bioavailability of citrus peel essential oils through increasing aqueous dispersibility, absorption, and stability in biological system. Essential oil constituents are both hydrophobic and volatile, which greatly constrains both their gastrointestinal absorption and therapeutic activities [69]. Chitosan and Alginate are biodegradable polymeric carriers that search to improve solubility of poorly soluble bioactive compounds, protecting them from premature degradation. Microcapsules have a relatively high product surface area (based on the particle size), which can facilitate increased permeation and absorption in the intestinal tract. Moreover, encapsulation can reduce the volatilization and oxidation of sensitive terpenes leading to an increase in systemic availability and prolonged pharmacological action of citrus peel essential oils as antidiabetic therapy [70].

Protection against Gastrointestinal Degradation

Microencapsulation serves as an efficient protector of citrus peel essential oils against the challenges posed by gastrointestinal conditions such as acidic environment, digestive enzymes and oxidative environments. Limonene and linalool are examples of volatile phytoconstituents that demonstrate high susceptibility to degradation after passage through the gastrointestinal tract, thus compromising therapeutic effects. Polymeric microcapsules serve as protective barriers to retard both premature release and chemical degradation of encapsulated oils. Four types of chitosan–alginate systems were created for pH-sensitive drugs. This improvement in gastrointestinal stability results in better retention of bioactive compounds and allows for effective intestinal absorption. Thus, microencapsulation can improve oral delivery performance and promotes better

antidiabetic efficacy of citrus peel essential oils [71].

Sustained Release and Enhanced Therapeutic Functionality

Microencapsulated citrus peel essential oils show sustained and controlled release pattern behaviour which improves the therapeutic efficacy and prolongs pharmacological action. Swelling, erosion and polymer relaxation affect the diffusion of encapsulated phytoconstituents through polymeric matrices. Sustained release is beneficial in addressing those issues by reducing the rapid dispersal of GLP-1 and providing constant concentrations of bioactive for hours, thus facilitating chronic glycemic control with fewer administrations. It also help avoid plasma concentration fluctuations with controlled release and ultimately improve patient compliance. Additionally, prolonged antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity contributes to improved protection against diabetes-associated oxidative stress and metabolic dysfunction. Such sustained release systems significantly enhance the overall therapeutic efficacy and stability of citrus peel essential oil-based antidiabetic formulations [72].

Functional Food and Nutraceutical Applications

One of these products that have attracted a lot of attention in terms of functional food and nutraceutical applications is microencapsulated citrus peel essential oils, due to their heightened stability and controlled release as well as preventive health effects. Why encapsulation is needed to enhance the insertion of essential oils into aqueous food systems, in addition to masking

unpleasant fragrance and inducing a minimum volatility. Encapsulated citrus oils can thus be utilized as health ingredients in functional beverages, dietary supplements, fortified foods, and nutraceutical products to exert antioxidant and antihyperglycemic activities. Moreover, microencapsulation increases shelf stability and safeguards sensitive phytoconstituents during the processing and storage of food. These systems offer a new avenue for producing natural and functional products with enhanced therapeutic and nutritional values [73].

Potential Role in Polyherbal Antidiabetic Formulations

The microencapsulated citrus peel essential oils show great potential for polyherbal antidiabetic applications due to their well-documented synergistic pharmacological activities with other herbal bioactives. The antioxidant, enzyme inhibitory, anti-inflammatory and insulin-sensitizing effects of medicinal plant extracts presented in diabetes may be complimented by the citrus oil constituents. Use of encapsulation provides compatibility between xenobiotic and phytoconstituents as well as improves the stability within complex herbal formulation. In addition, controlled release systems help provide sustained therapeutic activity and limit protein degradation in the body. The use of citrus peel essential oils in polyherbal microcapsule systems may have better synergistic efficacy, bioavailability, and compliance. Therefore, these kinds of multifunctional phytopharmaceutical formulations may be a hopeful approach for the safe and efficient long-term management of diabetes [74].

Table 3. Antidiabetic Applications of Microencapsulated Citrus Peel Essential Oils

Application Area	Mechanism/Role	Major Benefits	Pharmaceutical/Nutraceutical Significance
Enhancement of Bioavailability [75]	Improved solubility and intestinal absorption through polymeric encapsulation	Increased systemic availability and therapeutic efficacy	Better oral delivery of essential oil phytoconstituents
Protection Against Gastrointestinal Degradation [76]	Polymeric barrier protects oils from acidic pH and enzymatic degradation	Improved stability and retention of bioactive compounds	Enhanced gastrointestinal protection and absorption
Sustained Release and Therapeutic Performance [77]	Controlled diffusion and gradual release from polymer matrix	Prolonged pharmacological action and reduced dose frequency	Improved glycemic control and patient compliance
Functional Food and Nutraceutical Applications [78]	Incorporation into fortified foods and dietary supplements	Enhanced stability, shelf life, and antioxidant activity	Development of health-promoting functional products
Polyherbal Antidiabetic Formulations [79]	Synergistic interaction with herbal bioactives	Enhanced antihyperglycemic and antioxidant effects	Multifunctional phytopharmaceutical formulations for diabetes management

Safety, Toxicological Considerations, and Regulatory Aspects

Safety and regulatory evaluation are essential for the successful development of microencapsulated citrus peel essential oil formulations intended for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications [80]. Many reputable studies have established the biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low toxicity of chitosan and alginate as suitable drug delivery carriers. These polymers improve stability and reduce adverse biological responses of encapsulated compounds. Essential oils from citrus fruits have valuable therapeutic potentials, but excessive dermal absorption of the volatile terpenes component like limonene can lead to irritating, phototoxic and/or allergic skin reactions. Thus, conducting toxicological assessments such as cytotoxicity, genotoxicity and repeated-dose studies is essential for safety. Additional techniques such as encapsulation minimize direct exposure and oxidative degradation to improve safety. Complying with quality control, stability,

safety, and Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) regulations defined for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical products is necessary for regulatory approval [82].

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Despite significant advancements in microencapsulation technologies, several challenges limit the large-scale application of citrus peel essential oil formulations. The instability of drugs during storage, such as oxidation, volatilization of volatile components, moisture sensitivity and polymer degradation may give rise to poor therapeutic efficacy and limited shelf life. While microencapsulation processes are easy to implement in a laboratory, their up-scaling is often challenged by these factors: reproducibility, optimizing the process parameters, production cost and time at scale and equipment limitations. Furthermore, the variability of chemical composition among species, origins, climatic conditions and methods of extraction can affect both biological activity and

formulation performance. Moreover, clinical translation is still hampered by factors like lack of toxicological data, few human studies, regulatory hurdles and absence of well-established guidelines on dosage for long-term applications regarding pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

CONCLUSION

Microencapsulation of citrus peel EOs using Chitosan–Alginate systems is a promising and sustainable strategy to develop natural antidiabetic phytoconstituents into a more effective therapeutic agent. Citrus peel essential oils possess significant antioxidant, antihyperglycemic, anti-inflammatory, and insulin-sensitizing activities attributed to bioactive compounds such as limonene, linalool, and flavonoid-associated fractions. Direct pharmaceutical application is however limited by their volatility, oxidative stability and poor aqueous solubility. Chitosan–alginate polyelectrolyte complexes effectively improve encapsulation efficiency, gastrointestinal protection, controlled release and bioavailability of these volatile compounds. Although scale-up, standardization, and clinical translation still present challenges, future development of smart delivery systems and phytopharmaceuticals may eventually support the use of safe, effective, controlled-release natural-product-based pharmaceutical/cosmetic options to be employed as adjunctive therapies in chronic disease management such as diabetes.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Future advancements in microencapsulated citrus peel essential oil systems are expected to focus on smart and targeted delivery technologies for enhanced antidiabetic therapy. Microencapsulation is the method of trapping a liquid or solid into a polymeric membrane, allowing for the creation of stimuli-flexible

microcapsules that respond to basic pH, temperature, or enzymatic changes which can allow for selective and controlled delivery of bioactive phytoconstituents. Nano–micro hybrid encapsulation systems display benefits in increasing stability, bioavailability and multimodal therapeutic efficacy. Chitosan and Alginate can be used as building-blocks to construct targeted delivery platforms of antidiabetic agents, which might type robust hydrophilic carriers with improved intestinal absorptive properties and sustained release behaviour. Translation opportunities include incorporation into functional foods, nutraceuticals and phytopharmaceutical products. Innovative approaches for diabetes management may also include personalized herbal therapeutics based on intensified metabolic requirements of patients.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to the researchers and scholars whose published work on citrus peel essential oils, microencapsulation technologies, chitosan–alginate delivery systems, and natural antidiabetic therapeutics greatly contributed to the development of this review article. The authors further acknowledge the support provided by the online scientific databases, digital library facilities, and journal repositories of The Assam Royal Global University, which enabled access to relevant scientific literature essential for the preparation and finalization of this review. The authors also declare that no specific funding was received for this work from any governmental, commercial, or non-profit funding agency.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

DM: Diabetes Mellitus; T2DM: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus; CPEOs: Citrus Peel Essential Oils; ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species; AGEs: Advanced Glycation End Products; MAE: Microwave-Assisted Extraction; SFE: Supercritical Fluid Extraction; SC-CO₂: Supercritical Carbon Dioxide; AMPK: AMP-Activated Protein Kinase; GLUT-4: Glucose Transporter-4.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed Abdelhalim Yameny (2024). Diabetes mellitus overview 2024. *Journal of Bioscience and Applied Research*, 10(3), 641–645. <https://doi.org/10.21608/jbaar.2024.382794>.
2. Antar, S. A., Ashour, N. A., Sharaky, M., Khattab, M., Ashour, N. A., Zaid, R. T., Roh, E. J., Elkamhawy, A., & Al-Karmalawy, A. A. (2023). Diabetes mellitus: Classification, mediators, and complications; A gate to identify potential targets for the development of new effective treatments. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 168, 115734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2023.115734>.
3. Barbara Gieroba, Adrianna Kryska, & Anna Sroka-Bartnicka (2025). Type 2 diabetes mellitus – Conventional therapies and future perspectives in innovative treatment. *Biochemistry and Biophysics Reports*, 42, 102037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrep.2025.102037>.
4. Susilawati, E., Levita, J., Susilawati, Y., & Sumiwi, S. A. (2023). Review of the Case Reports on Metformin, Sulfonylurea, and Thiazolidinedione Therapies in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients. *Medical Sciences*, 11(3), 50. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medsci11030050>.
5. Saini, R. K., Ranjit, A., Sharma, K., Prasad, P., Shang, X., Gowda, K. G. M., & Keum, Y. S. (2022). Bioactive Compounds of Citrus Fruits: A Review of Composition and Health Benefits of Carotenoids, Flavonoids, Limonoids, and Terpenes. *Antioxidants* (Basel, Switzerland), 11(2), 239. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11020239>.
6. Lu, K., & Yip, Y. M. (2023). Therapeutic Potential of Bioactive Flavonoids from Citrus Fruit Peels toward Obesity and Diabetes Mellitus. *Future Pharmacology*, 3(1), 14-37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/futurepharmacol3010002>.
7. Balwinder Singh, Jatinder Pal Singh, Amritpal Kaur, & Narpinder Singh (2020). Phenolic composition, antioxidant potential and health benefits of citrus peel. *Food Research International*, 132, 109114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109114>.
8. Yilun Weng, Guangze Yang, Yang Li, Letao Xu, Xiaojing Chen, Hao Song, & Chun-Xia Zhao (2023). Alginate-based materials for enzyme encapsulation. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*, 318, 102957. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2023.102957>.
9. Patra, P., Upadhyay, T. K., Alshammari, N., Saeed, M., & Kesari, K. K. (2024). Alginate-Chitosan Biodegradable and Biocompatible Based Hydrogel for Breast Cancer Immunotherapy and Diagnosis: A Comprehensive Review. *ACS applied bio materials*, 7(6), 3515–3534. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsabm.3c00984>.
10. Wu, G., Terol, J., Ibanez, V. et al. Genomics of the origin and evolution of Citrus. *Nature* 554, 311–316 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature25447>.
11. Bora, H., Kamle, M., Mahato, D. K., Tiwari, P., & Kumar, P. (2020). Citrus Essential Oils (CEOs) and Their Applications in Food: An Overview. *Plants* (Basel, Switzerland), 9(3), 357. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9030357>.
12. Andrade, M. A., Barbosa, C. H., Shah, M. A., Ahmad, N., Vilarinho, F., Khwaldia, K., Silva,

- A. S., & Ramos, F. (2022). Citrus By-Products: Valuable Source of Bioactive Compounds for Food Applications. *Antioxidants* (Basel, Switzerland), 12(1), 38. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12010038>.
13. Nishala Erandi Wedamulla, Meiqi Fan, Young-Jin Choi, & Eun-Kyung Kim (2022). Citrus peel as a renewable bioresource: Transforming waste to food additives. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 95, 105163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2022.105163>.
14. Poonam Sharma, Reena Vishvakarma, Krishna Gautam, Archana Vimal, Vivek Kumar Gaur, Alvina Farooqui, Sunita Varjani, & Kaiser Younis (2022). Valorization of citrus peel waste for the sustainable production of value-added products. *Bioresource Technology*, 351, 127064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127064>.
15. Xie, Y., Zhang, L., Wu, W. et al. Sustainable and green extraction of citrus peel essential oil using intermittent solvent-free microwave technology. *Bioresour. Bioprocess.* 12, 48 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40643-025-00885-6>.
16. Irsha Dhotre (2025). A comprehensive review on progression and innovations in microwave assisted extraction technology for essential oils. *Journal of Chemical Technology & Biotechnology. Advance online publication.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.7823>.
17. Machado, C. A., Oliveira, F. O., de Andrade, M. A., Hodel, K. V. S., Lepikson, H., & Machado, B. A. S. (2022). Steam Distillation for Essential Oil Extraction: An Evaluation of Technological Advances Based on an Analysis of Patent Documents. *Sustainability*, 14(12), 7119. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127119>.
18. Waseem, R., Ayub, M. A., Anjam, M. T., Hussain, A., Bahadur, A., & Bibi, S. (2026). Superheated steam extraction and RSM-based optimization of antioxidant activity in Citrus paradisi essential oil and evaluation of antimicrobial activity. *Scientific reports*, 16(1), 5487. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-026-35099-z>.
19. Nayak, A., Shah, A., Bhatt, S., Bhushan, B., Kumar, A., Gaur, R., & Tyagi, I. (2026). Ultrasound and microwave assisted extraction of bioactives from food wastes: An overview on their comparative analysis towards commercialization. *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*, 124, 107712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2025.107712>.
20. Usman, M., Nakagawa, M., & Cheng, S. (2023). Emerging Trends in Green Extraction Techniques for Bioactive Natural Products. *Processes*, 11(12), 3444. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11123444>.
21. Herzyk, F., Piłakowska-Pietras, D., & Korzeniowska, M. (2024). Supercritical Extraction Techniques for Obtaining Biologically Active Substances from a Variety of Plant Byproducts. *Foods* (Basel, Switzerland), 13(11), 1713. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13111713>.
22. López-Hortas, L., Rodríguez, P., Díaz-Reinoso, B., Gaspar, M. C., de Sousa, H. C., Braga, M. E. M., & Domínguez, H. (2022). Supercritical fluid extraction as a suitable technology to recover bioactive compounds from flowers. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, 188, 105652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2022.105652>.
23. Ben Hsouna, A., Sadaka, C., Generalić Mekinić, I., Garzoli, S., Švarc-Gajić, J., Rodrigues, F., Morais, S., Moreira, M. M., Ferreira, E., Spigno, G., Brezo-Borjan, T., Akacha, B. B., Saad, R. B., Delerue-Matos, C., & Mnif, W. (2023). The Chemical Variability, Nutraceutical Value, and Food-Industry and Cosmetic Applications of Citrus Plants: A

- Critical Review. Antioxidants (Basel, Switzerland), 12(2), 481. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12020481>.
24. Benedetto, N., Carlucci, V., Faraone, I., Lela, L., Ponticelli, M., Russo, D., Mangieri, C., Tzvetkov, N. T., & Milella, L. (2023). An Insight into *Citrus medica* Linn.: A Systematic Review on Phytochemical Profile and Biological Activities. *Plants*, 12(12), 2267. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12122267>.
25. Ogunro, O.B., Richard, G., Izah, S.C., Ovuru, K.F., Babatunde, O.T., Das, M. (2024). Citrus aurantium: Phytochemistry, Therapeutic Potential, Safety Considerations, and Research Needs. In: Izah, S.C., Ogwu, M.C., Akram, M. (eds) *Herbal Medicine Phytochemistry. Reference Series in Phytochemistry*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43199-9_69.
26. El Aboubi M, Ben Hdech D, Bikri S, Benayad A, El Magri A, Aboussaleh Y, et al. Chemical composition of essential oils of Citrus limon peel from three Moroccan regions and their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic and dermatoprotective properties. *J Herbmed Pharmacol.* 2023;12(1):118-127. doi: 10.34172/jhp.2023.11.
27. J. W. G. Castro, G. G. de O. Souza, J. G. M. da Costa, and F. F. G. Rodrigues, "Citrus reticulata Blanco: A Review on Chemical Composition and Biological Activities." *Chemistry & Biodiversity* 23, no. 1 (2026): e03156. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202503156>.
28. Ashraf, H., Iahtisham-Ul-Haq, Butt, M. S., Nayik, G. A., Ramniwas, S., Damto, T., ... Ansari, M. J. (2024). Phytochemical and antioxidant profile of citrus peel extracts in relation to different extraction parameters. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 27(1), 286–299. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10942912.2024.2304274>.
29. Chakroun, I., Bouraoui, Z., Ayachi, T., Hosni, K., Guerbèj, H., Snoussi, M., Jebali, J., & Gharred, T. (2023). Phytochemical constituents and potential applications of Thomson Navel orange (*Citrus × aurantium* var. *sinensis* L.) peel extracts: Antioxidant, antimicrobial and antiproliferative properties. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 206, 117597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2023.117597>.
30. Diniso, T., Oriola, A. O., Adeyemi, J. O., Miya, G. M., Hosu, Y. S., Oyedeji, O. O., Kuria, S. K., & Oyedeji, A. O. (2024). Citrus wastes: A valuable raw material for biological applications. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 14(8), 11–26. <https://doi.org/10.7324/JAPS.2024.158781>.
31. Oh, Sehyuk, Park, Sanghun, Park, Gyutae, Choi, Nayoung, Kim, Chaeri, Lee, Solhee, Choi, Jungseok, Citrus sunki Peel Extract, Containing Nobiletin and Tangeretin, Enhances Proliferation and Differentiation in 3T3-L1 Adipocytes, *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 2024, 1027972, 17 pages, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/1027972>.
32. Lim, X. Y., Li, J., Yin, H. M., He, M., Li, L., & Zhang, T. (2023). Stabilization of Essential Oil: Polysaccharide-Based Drug Delivery System with Plant-like Structure Based on Biomimetic Concept. *Polymers*, 15(16), 3338. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15163338>.
33. Dedevas, T., Ekici, L., & Sagdic, O. (2022). Influence of Heating on Thermal Stability of Essential Oils During Storage. *Journal of Essential Oil-Bearing Plants*, 25(3), 611–625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0972060X.2022.2089058>.
34. Kadima Samuel Tshiyoyo, K. S., Rabbad, A., Yusuf, A. A., & Malgas, S. (2025). Combination of citrus peel-derived essential

- oils with acarbose to inhibit amylolytic enzymes – A potential type II diabetes treatment approach. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 306(Part 3), 141504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.141504>.
35. Bungau, S. G., Vesa, C. M., Bustea, C., Purza, A. L., Tit, D. M., Brisc, M. C., & Radu, A.-F. (2023). Antioxidant and Hypoglycemic Potential of Essential Oils in Diabetes Mellitus and Its Complications. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(22), 16501. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms242216501>.
36. Brahmi, F., Mokhtari, O., Legssyer, B., Hamdani, I., Asehrou, A., Hasnaoui, I., Rokni, Y., Diass, K., Oualdi, I., & Tahani, A. (2021). Chemical and biological characterization of essential oils extracted from citrus fruits peels. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 45(Part 8), 7794–7799. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.03.587>.
37. Munir, H., Yaqoob, S., Awan, K. A., Imtiaz, A., Naveed, H., Ahmad, N., Naeem, M., Sultan, W., & Ma, Y. (2024). Unveiling the Chemistry of Citrus Peel: Insights into Nutraceutical Potential and Therapeutic Applications. *Foods (Basel, Switzerland)*, 13(11), 1681. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13111681>.
38. Benayad, O., Bouhrim, M., Tiji, S., Kharchoufa, L., Addi, M., Drouet, S., Hano, C., Lorenzo, J. M., Bendaha, H., Bnouham, M., & Mimouni, M. (2021). Phytochemical Profile, α -Glucosidase, and α -Amylase Inhibition Potential and Toxicity Evaluation of Extracts from Citrus aurantium (L) Peel, a Valuable By-Product from Northeastern Morocco. *Biomolecules*, 11(11), 1555. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11111555>.
39. Li, Y., Li, W., Ye, Z., Ji, C., & Zhou, Z. (2024). Antioxidant, Anti-Inflammatory, and Anticancer Activities of Five Citrus Peel Essential Oils. *Antioxidants (Basel, Switzerland)*, 13(12), 1562. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox13121562>.
40. Elkouch Asmae, El Aboubi Meriam, Bikri Samir, Aboussaleh Youssef, Abdellatif Bour. Mitigating Hyperglycemia-Induced learning and memory impairment: Insulin Combined with Lemon Peel Essential Oil effects on Hippocampal Oxidative Stress, Neuroinflammation, and BDNF Expression in Type 1 Diabetic Rats. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2025;18(6):2537-7. doi: 10.52711/0974-360X.2025.00363.
41. Durmus, N., Gulsunoglu-Konuskan, Z., & Kilic-Akyilmaz, M. (2024). Recovery, Bioactivity, and Utilization of Bioactive Phenolic Compounds in Citrus Peel. *Food science & nutrition*, 12(12), 9974–9997. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.4570>.
42. Elhawary, E.A., Nilofar, N., Zengin, G. et al. Variation of the essential oil components of Citrus aurantium leaves upon using different distillation techniques and evaluation of their antioxidant, antidiabetic, and neuroprotective effect against Alzheimer’s disease. *BMC Complement Med Ther* 24, 73 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-024-04380-x>.
43. Sousa, V. I., Parente, J. F., Marques, J. F., Forte, M. A., & Tavares, C. J. (2022). Microencapsulation of Essential Oils: A Review. *Polymers*, 14(9), 1730. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14091730>.
44. Fernandes, B., Oliveira, M. C., Marques, A. C., dos Santos, R. G., & Serrano, C. (2024). Microencapsulation of Essential Oils and Oleoresins: Applications in Food Products. *Foods*, 13(23), 3873. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13233873>.
45. Sacco, P., Pedroso-Santana, S., Kumar, Y., Joly, N., Martin, P., & Bocchetta, P. (2021). Ionotropic Gelation of Chitosan Flat Structures

- and Potential Applications. *Molecules*, 26(3), 660.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26030660>.
46. Mehta, N., Kumar, P., Verma, A. K., Umaraw, P., Kumar, Y., Malav, O. P., Sazili, A. Q., Domínguez, R., & Lorenzo, J. M. (2022). Microencapsulation as a Noble Technique for the Application of Bioactive Compounds in the Food Industry: A Comprehensive Review. *Applied Sciences*, 12(3), 1424. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12031424>.
47. Weng, Y., Serrano, T., Magallanes, K., Bekker, M., & Baldelli, A. (2026). Locking in flavor: Aroma chemistry and spray drying encapsulation strategies for stable food applications. *Food Chemistry*, 513, 148598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2026.148598>.
48. Napiórkowska, A., & Kurek, M. (2022). Coacervation as a Novel Method of Microencapsulation of Essential Oils-A Review. *Molecules* (Basel, Switzerland), 27(16), 5142. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27165142>.
49. Kučuk, N., Primožič, M., Knez, Ž., & Leitgeb, M. (2024). Alginate Beads with Encapsulated Bioactive Substances from *Mangifera indica* Peels as Promising Peroral Delivery Systems. *Foods*, 13(15), 2404. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13152404>.
50. Gadziński, P., Froelich, A., Jadach, B., Wojtyłko, M., Tatarek, A., Białek, A., Kryzstofiak, J., Gackowski, M., Otto, F., & Osmałek, T. (2022). Iontropic Gelation and Chemical Crosslinking as Methods for Fabrication of Modified-Release Gellan Gum-Based Drug Delivery Systems. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(1), 108. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15010108>.
51. Vieira, T. M., Moldão-Martins, M., & Alves, V. D. (2021). Design of Chitosan and Alginate Emulsion-Based Formulations for the Production of Monolayer Crosslinked Edible Films and Coatings. *Foods*, 10(7), 1654. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10071654>.
52. Mangope, K., Kaseke, T., & Fawole, O. A. (2025). Spray-drying microencapsulation of fixed oils: An innovative and sustainable technology to enhance oxidative stability, functionality and application in food systems. *Applied Food Research*, 5(2), 101200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afres.2025.101200>.
53. Indriyani, N. N., Al-Anshori, J., Wahyudi, T., Nurzaman, M., Nurjanah, S., Permadi, N., & Julaeha, E. (2024). An optimized chitosan/alginate-based microencapsulation of lime peel essential oil and its application as an antibacterial textile. *Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition*, 35(7), 989–1007. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09205063.2024.2313829>.
54. Berraaouan, D., Essifi, K., Addi, M., Hano, C., Fauconnier, M. L., & Tahani, A. (2023). Hybrid Microcapsules for Encapsulation and Controlled Release of Rosemary Essential Oil. *Polymers*, 15(4), 823. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15040823>.
55. Wani, S. U. D., Ali, M., Mehdi, S., Masoodi, M. H., Zargar, M. I., & Shakeel, F. (2023). A review on chitosan and alginate-based microcapsules: Mechanism and applications in drug delivery systems. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 248, 125875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.125875>.
56. Oprea, I., Fărcaș, A. C., Leopold, L. F., Diaconeasa, Z., Coman, C., & Socaci, S. A. (2022). Nano-Encapsulation of Citrus Essential Oils: Methods and Applications of Interest for the Food Sector. *Polymers*, 14(21), 4505. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14214505>.

57. Razola-Díaz, M. del C., Guerra-Hernández, E. J., García-Villanova, B., & Verardo, V. (2021). Recent developments in extraction and encapsulation techniques of orange essential oil. *Food Chemistry*, 354, 129575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.129575>.
58. Majewska-Smolarek, K., & Kowalewska, A. (2025). Essential Oils as Green Antibacterial Modifiers of Polymeric Materials. *Polymers*, 17(21), 2924. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17212924>.
59. Šafranko, S., Šubarić, D., Jerković, I., & Jokić, S. (2023). Citrus By-Products as a Valuable Source of Biologically Active Compounds with Promising Pharmaceutical, Biological and Biomedical Potential. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel, Switzerland)*, 16(8), 1081. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph16081081>.
60. Aguado, R. J., Mazega, A., Tarrés, Q., & Delgado-Aguilar, M. (2023). The role of electrostatic interactions of anionic and cationic cellulose derivatives for industrial applications: A critical review. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 201, 116898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2023.116898>.
61. Zhao, Y., Wang, Y., Zhang, Z., & Li, H. (2023). Advances in Controllable Release Essential Oil Microcapsules and Their Promising Applications. *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, 28(13), 4979. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28134979>.
62. Julaeha, E., Puspita, W. R., Permadi, N., Harja, A., Nurjanah, S., Wahyudi, T., & Al-Anshori, J. (2024). Optimization of Citrus aurantifolia peel extract encapsulation in alginate-gelatin hydrogel microbeads for antibacterial wound dressing applications. *Carbohydrate Polymer Technologies and Applications*, 7, 100406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carpta.2023.100406>.
63. Frenț, O. D., Duteanu, N., Teusdea, A. C., Ciocan, S., Vicaș, L., Jurca, T., Muresan, M., Pallag, A., Ianasi, P., & Marian, E. (2022). Preparation and Characterization of Chitosan-Alginate Microspheres Loaded with Quercetin. *Polymers*, 14(3), 490. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14030490>.
64. Villate, A., San Nicolas, M., Olivares, M., Aizpurua-Olaizola, O., & Usobiaga, A. (2023). Chitosan-Coated Alginate Microcapsules of a Full-Spectrum Cannabis Extract: Characterization, Long-Term Stability and In Vitro Bioaccessibility. *Pharmaceutics*, 15(3), 859. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15030859>.
65. Zambrano, V., Bustos, R., Arozarena, Y., & Mahn, A. (2023). Optimization of a Microencapsulation Process Using Oil-in-Water (O/W) Emulsion to Increase Thermal Stability of Sulforaphane. *Foods (Basel, Switzerland)*, 12(20), 3869. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12203869>.
66. Song, Y., Gu, Y., Ren, A., Li, X., Wu, S., Gong, Y., & Luo, Y. (2025). Optimization and Comprehensive Characterization of the Microencapsulation Process for Taro Essence. *Foods*, 14(5), 754. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14050754>.
67. Ali, A. M., Gabbar, M. A., Abdel-Twab, S. M., Fahmy, E. M., Ebaid, H., Alhazza, I. M., & Ahmed, O. M. (2020). Antidiabetic Potency, Antioxidant Effects, and Mode of Actions of Citrus reticulata Fruit Peel Hydroethanolic Extract, Hesperidin, and Quercetin in Nicotinamide/Streptozotocin-Induced Wistar Diabetic Rats. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*, 2020, 1730492. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1730492>.
68. Sheelmareva, F. A., Vasall, P. R. N., Permadi, N., Harja, A., Nurjanah, S., Al-Anshori, J., & Julaeha, E. (2025). Composition and medicinal

- applications of Citrus essential oils: Current insights and future perspectives. *Phytomedicine Plus*, 5(3), 100836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyflu.2025.100836>.
69. Djihad, N., Naima, F. O., Petronilho, S., Hamid, S., Bedjou, F. N. E., & Coimbra, M. A. (2024). Microencapsulation of Citrus limon essential oil by complex coacervation and release behavior of terpenic and derived volatile compounds. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 152, 109830. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2024.109830>.
70. Ali Redha, A., Kodikara, C., & Cozzolino, D. (2024). Does Encapsulation Improve the Bioavailability of Polyphenols in Humans? A Concise Review Based on In Vivo Human Studies. *Nutrients*, 16(21), 3625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu16213625>.
71. Ambrosio CMS, Alvim ID, Wen C, Gómez Expósito R, Aalvink S, Contreras Castillo CJ, Da Gloria EM and Smidt H (2022) Exploring the effect of a microencapsulated citrus essential oil on in vitro fermentation kinetics of pig gut microbiota. *Front. Microbiol.* 13:952706. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2022.952706.
72. Ahmed, S., Hu, G., & Batool, Z. (2026). Advances in protein-based microencapsulation: From encapsulation materials to functional applications and future prospects. *Food Chemistry*, 508(Part A), 148299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2026.148299>.
73. Obayomi, O. V., Edo, G. I., Dada, A. O., & Dokouhaki, M. (2026). Advanced encapsulation technologies for functional foods: Enhancing stability, bioavailability, and controlled release of nutraceuticals and bioactives. *Applied Food Research*, 6(1), 101622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afres.2025.101622>.
74. Paul, S., & Majumdar, M. (2023). Exploring antidiabetic potential of a polyherbal formulation Madhurakshak Activ: An in vitro and in silico study. *Fitoterapia*, 169, 105598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2023.105598>
75. Cabanillas-Ponce de León, R., Cardenas-Torres, F. I., Ontiveros, N., Contreras-Angulo, L. A., Elisande-Romero, C. A., Leyva-López, N., Bernal-Millán, M. d. J., Heredia, J. B., & Gutiérrez-Grijalva, E. P. (2025). Advancements in Encapsulation Technologies: The Potential of Polyphenols as an Antidiabetic Therapy. *Scientia Pharmaceutica*, 93(4), 55. <https://doi.org/10.3390/scipharm93040055>.
76. Suresh, V., Shams, R., Dash, K. K., Shaikh, A. M., & Béla, K. (2025). Comprehensive review on enzymatic polymer degradation: A sustainable solution for plastics. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 20, 101788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2025.101788>.
77. Yihan, W., Jinjin, D., Yingqi, W., Guanai, M., & Xiwu, Z. (2025). Advances in plant essential oils and drug delivery systems for skincare. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 16, 1578280. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2025.1578280>.
78. Chávez-Delgado, E. L., & Jacobo-Velázquez, D. A. (2023). Essential Oils: Recent Advances on Their Dual Role as Food Preservatives and Nutraceuticals against the Metabolic Syndrome. *Foods*, 12(5), 1079. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12051079>.
79. Kambale, E. K., Quetin-Leclercq, J., Memvanga, P. B., & Beloqui, A. (2022). An Overview of Herbal-Based Antidiabetic Drug Delivery Systems: Focus on Lipid- and Inorganic-Based Nanoformulations. *Pharmaceutics*, 14(10), 2135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14102135>.
80. Dosoky, N. S., & Setzer, W. N. (2018). Biological Activities and Safety of Citrus spp.

Essential Oils. International journal of molecular sciences, 19(7), 1966. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms19071966>.

81. Jackson-Davis, A., White, S., Kassama, L. S., Coleman, S., Shaw, A., Mendonca, A., Cooper, B., Thomas-Popo, E., Gordon, K., & London, L. (2023). A review of regulatory standards and advances in essential oils as antimicrobials in foods. *Journal of Food Protection*, 86(2), 100025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfp.2022.100025>.
82. Brah, A. S., Armah, F. A., Obuah, C., Akwetey, S. A., & Adokoh, C. K. (2023). Toxicity and therapeutic applications of citrus essential oils (CEOs): a review. *International Journal of Food Properties*, 26(1), 301–326. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10942912.2022.2158864>.

HOW TO CITE: Parampara Barman, Bipul Nath*, Yeduru Krishna Reddy, Swagata Chetia, Microencapsulation of Citrus Peel Essential Oils Using Chitosan–Alginate Systems: Mechanistic Insights and Antidiabetic Applications, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 5120-5143. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20302771>

